

ANNEX OF THE PAPER ENTITLED “A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE USE OF BIG DATA FOR SUSTAINABLE TOURISM”

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1. Introduction

In this document, we provide some supplementary material for the systematic literature review (SLR) on the use of Big Data for Sustainable Tourism reported in the paper:

Rahmadian, E., Feitosa, D., Zwitter. (2020). , A.: A systematic literature review on the use of big data for sustainable tourism.

In particular, we present the list of primary studies included in the SLR.

2. Primary Studies

In the following, we present the list of primary studies included in the SLR. We assigned an ID to each primary study, which are used in the reporting of the SLR when referencing the studies.

1. de Oliveira Lima, T., Júnior, M.C., de J. Prado, K.H., dos S. Júnior, A. (2019). A Big Data Experiment to Assess the Effectiveness of Deep Learning Neural Networks in the Mining of Sustainable Aspects of the Hotels Clients Opinions. In: Latifi, S. (ed.) 16th International Conference on Information Technology-New Generations (ITNG '19). vol. 800, pp. 201–20k. *Springer International Publishing*.
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